

Interface between anode porous transport layer and catalyst layer: a key to efficient, stable and competitive proton exchange membrane water electrolysis

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Highlights:

- Coating anode PTL with Pt or Ir is crucial to ensure long-term stability
- Ir coating can fulfil the function of the catalyst
- Combination of Pt or Ir coating and low-loading catalyst layer enhances performance
- Nano-structuring of the PTL surface has positive impact on the performance
- Time stability of low Ir content systems needs more attention

Graphical abstract:

Abstract

This review examines recent advancements in the design and optimisation of the anode porous transport layer (PTL) and catalyst layer (CL) interface in proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE). The quality of PTL-CL interface (contact area and contact resistivity per unit area) is critical to overall electrolyser performance, influencing both the (activation and ohmic) voltage losses and stability. To

mitigate issues associated with Ti PTL passivation and enhance charge transport, various noble metal coatings, including Pt, Au, and Ir, have been explored. Ir coatings have shown to be the optimal solution due to their stability and catalytic activity. The review highlights surface modification techniques such as physical vapor deposition, electroplating, and laser ablation, as well as the development of porous transport electrodes (PTEs) and microporous layers (MPLs). These approaches aim to optimise the performance of the electrolyser while minimising the noble metal usage. The findings underscore the importance of material choice and surface nano/micro scale morphology of the interface in achieving cost-effective and durable PEMWE systems.

1 Introduction

Proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE), alongside other green hydrogen production methods, is gaining increased relevance in today's political climate. In March 2023, the Council of the European Union agreed to increase renewable energy use in the industrial sector by 1.6% annually. By 2030, 42% of hydrogen used in industry should come from renewable sources, rising to 60% by 2035 [1]. Thus, developing cost-effective and reliable hydrogen generating technologies is crucial for meeting these ambitious goals.

Compared to other technologies, PEMWE produces highly pure hydrogen at high current densities with relatively compact devices capable of operating under increased pressure. However, the primary drawback of PEMWE is the high investment cost due to the use of expensive construction materials. On the cathode side, a traditional carbon supported Pt nanoparticles in combination with carbon based PTL similar to those used in PEM fuel cell technology is used. The harsh conditions present on the anode side, caused by the high acidity of a membrane and high anode potentials, however, necessitate the use of corrosion-resistant materials such as Ti and Pt-group metals (PGM). Ti is used for bipolar plates and the anode porous transport layer (PTL). The latter can be either in the form of sintered material or felt. PGMs are used as catalysts in catalyst layer (CL) deposited on the membrane. The oxidative environment in the anode compartment causes the formation of a compact surface oxide on the Ti leading to significant contact resistance between PTL and catalyst layer resulting in PEMWE performance decay. To avoid this effect and ensure its long-term stable operation, the PTL is generally coated with a PGM layer. This further increases the already high consumption of PMGs.

To address this issue, it is essential to develop a smartly designed PTL-CL interface. This may involve creating functional surface morphologies on the PTL through nanostructuring of the coating and/or the use of a microporous layer (MPL). Such an optimised interface enables minimising loading of PGMs while

maintaining high effectiveness and efficiency. This review highlights cutting-edge research in this area, with a particular emphasis on publications from the years 2022-2024.

2 Porous transport layer surface treatment and coating

The PTL-CL interface significantly impacts the overall electrolyser performance. Not only it is necessary to carefully design the morphology of the PTL to avoid unnecessary voltage losses connected to mass transport, but it is also important to pay attention to its charge transport properties. Figure 1 schematically summarizes individual approaches used to improve PTL-CL interface properties when compared to the pristine PTL discussed later on in the text.

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of porous transport layer – catalyst layer interface modifications. Impact on the electrolysis load curve is indicated as well. Individual methods shown are noted in the figure.

2.1 Coatings for excessive passivation protection

During PEMWE operation, a resistive Ti oxide forms on the anode Ti PTL surface, causing rapid performance degradation. Rakousky et al. [2] reported that after operation at 2 A cm^{-2} for 1 000 h, the ohmic voltage losses arising from Ti PTL passivation accounted for 78% of the overall voltage losses. Moreover, current flow through the poorly conductive Ti oxide generates heat, creating hot spots that cause damage to the CL and leading to its delamination [3, 4]. Data from multiple reports also show less efficient utilisation of the catalyst within CL is when anode Ti PTL without any surface treatment is used, resulting in higher activation voltage losses [2, 5, 6].

To mitigate these issues, the anode PTLs in PEMWE are usually coated with a thin layer of PGM (Au, Pt or Ir). Pt [2, 6-9] and Au [6, 9, 10] coatings only protect the Ti PTL against oxidation. Pt coatings are preferable as they provide excellent long-term stability to the anode PTL-CL interface, unlike Au which is prone to

dissolution [6, 9]. Ir and Ir-based [3-6, 9, 11-19] coatings provide not only reliable protection to the PTL but also catalytic activity for oxygen evolution reaction. In addition to pure Ir, co-deposition of IrO₂ and TiO₂, as well as more sophisticated mixed oxides containing Ti, Ir and Ta were explored as well [16-18].

Before applying PMG coatings, many researchers perform a chemical pre-treatment of the Ti PTL using various acids or etchants, such as oxalic acid [12, 16, 17] or HCl [18-20]. These treatments allow removing the native oxide layer present on the Ti surface, thus reducing the contact resistance between the PTL and CL and ensure better reproducibility of results [19]. Further decrease of the interfacial resistance can be achieved by employing additional pre-treatments to the surface. In our recent work, it was demonstrated that introducing a thin layer of (electro)chemically formed Ti hydride on the Ti PTL surface significantly decreases the ohmic resistance of the electrolyser cell [19-21]. While the surface hydride partially stabilises the PTL against oxidation [19, 20], it was not sufficiently stable for practical application. However, combining surface hydridation with subsequent Ir coating resulted in both very low contact resistance and reliable stability [19].

Coating formation is most commonly achieved through physical vapour deposition techniques, such as arc plasma deposition [11, 15, 22] or sputter coating [2-7, 9, 14, 19] and less commonly, electroplating [8, 10, 12, 13]. For depositing oxide coatings, thermal decomposition of precursors sprayed onto the PTL is used [16-18]. Kang et al. compared the quality of Au and Ir coatings made by sputter coating and electroplating [10, 13]. The electroplated coatings showed better quality, featuring a micro-structured surface without cracks (corresponding PTLs allowed for better performance and stability of the PEMWE). However, it is important to note that their results on sputter-coated PTLs are not in agreement with existing literature, as many researchers report good and reliable performance for sputter-coated PTLs.

The amounts of deposited PGMs vary across studies. In reports on Pt and Au, the loadings range from 0.2 to 0.9 and 0.2 to 0.8 mg_{PGM} cm⁻², respectively. Studies dedicated to Ir coatings use loadings from 0.02 to 0.9 mg_{Ir} cm⁻². In this context, Liu et al. published a series of impactful papers on sputter coating of anode PTLs [4, 5, 9]. In experiments employing 4 000 h long PEMWE operation, their findings identified Ir as the most suitable material for PTL coating due to its stability and catalytic activity [9]. Most importantly, they showed that Ir loading above 0.025 mg_{Ir} cm⁻² (corresponding to 13 nm thickness) does not influence the electrochemical performance of the electrolyser [5]. Similarly, Srour et al. reported that 0.02 mg_{Ir} cm⁻² of Ir is a sufficient for a functional coating [6]. Given that the state-of-the-art Ir loading ranges between 0.34 and 2 mg_{Ir} cm⁻² [17], if done properly, the amount of Ir needed to effectively protect the Ti surface of the PTL is almost negligible.

The fact that protective coating of PTL is crucial for PEMWE stability is acknowledged by the market, offering several commercial solutions in PGM-coated PTLs. For example, Bekaert, TANAKA, and TOPTITECH offer heavily Pt-coated Ti felts for use in PEMWE, though the information about PGM loading is, in this case, not always available.

2.2 Protective coating as a catalyst

To minimise the consumption of noble metals, some studies have reported using Ir coatings on PTLs as the catalyst, eliminating the need for the anode CL on the membrane [11-14]. This component is referred to as a porous transport electrode (PTE). These studies used between 0.085 and 0.5 mg_{Ir} cm⁻² (coatings prepared by electroplating [12, 13] and physical vapour deposition techniques [11, 14]), achieving good performances between 1.8 and 1.9 V at 2 A cm⁻². Furthermore, the utilisation of the Ir in this design is significantly more effective, as reported by Yu et al [12]. In their study, the Ir mass-specific current density at 1.7 V was 14 times higher with the Ir-coated PTE compared to the PTL with an anode CL on the membrane.

The disadvantage of PTEs appears to be poor stability during operation [11, 13]. However, this is not the case for the PTE developed by Lee et al. In their notable studies [7, 14], they used laser ablation to pretreat the PTL surface before PGM coating. This treatment partially melts the surface of the sintered Ti material, closes off the smallest pores, and creates a more uniform surface, effectively forming a microporous layer. The researchers explored PEMWE using low loadings of Ir. First, the laser-treated sintered Ti was coated with Pt and used as a PTL in combination with a low-loading CL (0.055 mg_{Ir} cm⁻²), reaching 1.9 V at 2 A cm⁻² [7]. In the second study, the laser-treated sintered Ti was coated with Ir and used as a PTE (0.085 mg_{Ir} cm⁻²), achieving 1.84 V at 2 A cm⁻² and showing stable performance in an accelerated stress test [14].

2.3 Protective coating combined with a catalyst layer

Advantageous approach represents application of a PGM-coated PTL in combination with CL allowing reduction of PGM loading in CL. In this configuration, the low in-plane conductivity of the low-loading CL on the membrane is bridged by the highly conductive PGM layer on the PTL, enabling good performance. In a series of noteworthy papers [11, 15, 22], Yasutake et al. developed a nanostructured surface for Ti felt PTL. Through a chemical treatment in NaOH followed by heat treatment, they formed TiO₂ nano-needles on the PTL surface. Obtained surface was then coated with a thin layer of Ir (0.3 mg_{Ir} cm⁻²) via arc plasma deposition. Initially, these PTLs were used as PTEs, without using a CL on the anode side [11]. These cells exhibited satisfactory performance of 1.83 V at 2 A cm⁻²; even though, the system showed

insufficient stability. Interestingly, combining these nanostructured Ir-coated PTLs with a low-loading CL ($0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Ir}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) resulted in an impressive electrolyser performance (1.63 V at 2 A cm^{-2}) [15]. Additionally, the intricate surface nanomorphology of the PTL allows for operation at very high current densities (20 A cm^{-2}) without the influence of mass transport resistance [15].

The interplay between a CL with sub-optimal charge transport properties and a PGM-coated PTL was also described by Bernt et al. [8]. They fabricated a CCM using $\text{IrO}(\text{OH})_x$ anode catalyst. Despite having lower conductivity, the particles of $\text{IrO}(\text{OH})_x$ have a lower packing density and high activity compared to the commonly used IrO_2 , allowing for the use of reduced Ir loadings ($0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Ir}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). By using this CCM in combination with a Pt-electroplated anode PTL, the electrolyser reached 1.62 V at 2 A cm^{-2} , outperforming the benchmark assembly using Pt-coated anode PTL and a CL with IrO_2 (loading $2.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Ir}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$).

3 Microporous layer – interlayer between PTL and CL

One of the main contributing factors to the cell performance loss is PTL passivation in contact with IrO_2 catalyst and nonhomogeneous distribution of local current densities, due to sparse interface between PTL and CL. Additionally, this aspect may lead to local hot-spots formation and reduction of the MEA life-time. Therefore, in the last decade, a significant scientific effort was focused on the fabrication of microporous layers (MPL) on PTL, in a same manner as in fuel cell gas-diffusion layers. Two main approaches were used; one with MPL based on supposedly corrosion-resistant ceramic materials which would also protect PTL [23-26] and second, arguably more feasible, based on introducing the MPL composed of Ti particles with subsequent sintering step [27-30]. Former approach has significant issues connected to ceramic material conductivity and stability. The latter approach leads to preparation of single-phase MPL/PTL with gradient porosity and surface of MPL itself can be further treated to improve corrosion resistance. Adding MPL to PTL significantly enhances performance of PEM water electrolyser [30, 31]. This can be further improved PGM coating on MPL and use of CCM setup during the cell assembly [30]. Smaller pore openings and smoother surface structure of MPL in comparison with PTL leads to formation of much more numerous contact points between CL and MPL/PTL [32]. This improves not only local current density distribution, but also the in-plane electron contact between IrO_2 and Ti, enabling higher utilisation of IrO_2 [29-31, 33].

4 Conclusion

This review explores advances in anode PTL-CL interface for PEM water electrolysis, emphasising its role in enhancing performance and stability. Coating PTLs with Ir or Pt is crucial for ensuring stable operation.

Leveraging the catalytic activity of Ir coatings has led to advanced concepts like porous transport electrodes, significantly reducing Pt-group metal consumption. Precious metal PTL coatings also enable the use of CLs with poor in-plane conductivity due to low catalyst loadings or poorly conducting catalysts. Further performance improvements can be achieved by focusing on the PTL-CL interface morphology. Approaches such as chemical nanostructuring, laser ablation, and the use of MPLs substantially enhance the catalyst active area. However, some studies indicate that long-term stability may be a challenge for these solutions, and many papers lack data on the stability of these systems or use testing conditions not relevant to real-world applications.

In conclusion, advancing PTL-CL interface design is pivotal for the further development of PEM water electrolysis technology, promising significant reductions in noble metal consumption and operational costs. Further studies should be focused on long-term stability of the systems with reduced PGM loading.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve the language and readability of certain parts of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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